

“Sustainify” Worksheet: Course redesign within existing program

This template serves to help redesign or modify a course (e.g. 6-12 weeks of teaching) following the Sustainify guideline (<https://zenodo.org/records/14217352>).

It is designed to be supportive, so please adapt it to your needs such that it is most useful to your intentions and goals. It could be used on program level with adaptation.

1. Course Relation to Sustainability

Overall course topic to teach	
Intention (main focus, or related)	
Relatable SDGs	
Relevant SDG Targets addressed	
Result: New short description of course (that refers to sustainability)	

2. Reflection in the syllabus (course description): Learning objectives

Make sure to use wording that reflects the type of learning objective.

Learning objective	Way of Instruction	Assessment
Knowledge and Understanding <i>(e.g., student knows, is aware of, has an overview of, understands, ...)</i>		
Competence and Skills <i>(e.g., student is capable of, can model, can design, ...)</i>		
Judgement and Approach <i>(e.g. student can assess, compare, argue, ...)</i>		

3. Sustainability Competencies to be taught within the course

The GreenComp framework provides 12 competencies. The way of instruction and assessment are intended to refer to the previous table if it can be integrated. Please make sure to argue how it specifically addresses the sustainability skill in those cases.

Sustainability competencies per area		Way of Instruction	Assessment
Embodying sustainability values	Valuing sustainability		
	Supporting fairness		
	Promoting nature		
Embracing complexity in sustainability	Systems thinking		
	Critical thinking		
	Problem framing		
Envisioning sustainable futures	Futures literacy		
	Adaptability		
	Exploratory thinking		
Acting for sustainability	Political agency		
	Collective action		
	Individual initiative		

4. Individual Topics to Cover within the Course

Please provide a list of the sustainability-related topics intended to be taught with SDG reference and/or sustainability dimension.

5. Teaching Methods Planned for Use

Please refer to the methods mentioned in Tables 2 and 3 and provide more details.

Teaching method	Additional notes about implementation

6. Evaluation and assessment of sustainability integration

Consider and include both formative and reflective assessments. Please refer to the assessments mentioned in Table 3 and provide more details as appropriate.

Assessment methods	Additional notes about implementation
Formative:	
Reflective:	

7. Student feedback

Discussion of the modifications with current students to get their perspective.

Student concern/idea	Reflection of instructor	Conclusion

Final reflections